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All the Light We Cannot See: The Search for Dark Photons

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1 Abstract

A long-standing puzzle in our universe is the existence of dark matter (DM), a kind of matter that does not interact significantly with ordinary matter but that is confirmed by a series of astrophysical and cosmological observations, including in the stunning recent pictures from James Webb Space Telescope. The dominance of this DM over ordinary matter remains one of the main questions for high energy physics and astrophysics. Particle physicists are working on models that can ameliorate our understanding of fundamental interactions, and to reconcile DM with the Standard Model. Dark Photons (DPs) could be the key in developing Beyond Standard Model (BSM) theories. DPs are hypothesised hidden sector gauge bosons, akin to the photon. Neutral under Standard Model interactions, DPs can be detected due to kinetic mixing with the ordinary photon. A few theoretical models postulate the existence of a DP, further classifying them as either massive or light.

Energy deposits in the calorimeter are collected as objects termed jets, as a proxy for initiating quarks and gluons. In this project, we looked at novel topologies involving leptons in large-radius jets and mono-lepton jets respectively, and performed initial feasibility studies of the final states.

2 Introduction

The Standard Model (SM) [1,2], is insufficient in explaining all particles and particle interactions. Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) and Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) explain the electromagnetic, weak and strong interactions and form the basis of the SM. We have been exploring Beyond Standard Model (BSM) theories that can explain and solve some of the problems in the SM. These theories range in complexity, and strongly support some kind of "theory of everything". To date, there has been no evidence that some of these more popular theories, like Supersymmetry, String Theory and Quantum Loop Gravity, have any experimental or physical basis.

Dark matter is arguably the biggest proof that the SM is incomplete [3]. Based on astronomical observation, we expect 27% of the matter in the Universe to be classified as "dark" [4]. This matter only interacts with baryonic ("visible") matter gravitationally, and not via the three other fundamental forces. This opens up an entire hidden (dark) sector of physics that has not been experimentally observed or studied. The theories of particles comprising dark sector are varied and in-depth, and have their own possible ways of being observed experimentally, either directly or indirectly [5].

We start this project by looking into some theoretical aspects of the dark photon, a hypothesised hidden sector particle. We introduce our two models, one using a detector-object known as a Semi-Visible Jet (SVJ), and one using a different detection signature known as a mono-lepton jet. In our both our models, the DP decays into two leptons and we discuss the detection signatures that would be produced by the ATLAS detector at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN. We performed an initial feasibility study for both models.

3 Dark Photons

BSM particles were originally thought to be charged under some of the gauge interactions of the SM particles. The dark (hidden) sector, however, is not charged under the SM gauge group. Dark states can still interact with the SM particles in a Yukawa-like interaction, or by mediation by a dark gauge boson (or both) [5].

The dark photon is a hypothetical dark gauge boson that arises from a symmetry of a hypothetical dark sector comprising particles that are completely neutral under the SM interactions. Dark and normal matter can interact through some portal, which can be experimentally accessible. The portals are classified by the type and dimension of the operators, which places a huge importance on the spin of the mediator. We classify dark photons as a spin-1 vector boson, and the vector portal allows the interaction between normal and dark matter to take place because of the kinetic mixing between one dark gauge boson, and one visible Abelian gauge boson [5]. The two gauge bosons go directly into each other as they propagate, and the kinetic mixing is therefore a portal that links the dark and visible sectors, making it experimentally accessible [5].

There are two classes of Dark Photons that have been theorised: massive DPs and massless DPs. In this project, we only considered massive DPs. Since massive DPs couple directly to SM currents, they are easier to observe in experimental (particle) searches. More specifically, the massive DP couples directly to the SM electromagnetic current. As such, the massive DP can be classified as a very light vector boson.

The phenomenology of the massive DP is extensive, and the general Lagrangian is given by:

$$L = -\epsilon e J^\mu A'_\mu$$

In the above equation, J^μ is the electromagnetic (EM) current, giving rise to the use of "photon" to describe this hypothesised hidden sector particle. Since J^μ is the same current as the EM current, the production, decay and detection modes of the DP are similar to those of the SM photon. Four possible production modes are Bremsstrahlung, annihilation, hypothetical dark meson decays and the Drell-Yan production mechanism [5]. In both models considered in this project, the DP decays into a lepton pair.

Massive DPs are then split into two further categories: visible or invisible, based on their mass limit. The DPs need to decay into SM charged states, in our case the leptons, for them to be visible in the detector. To emphasise this point, the DP is only visible through its decay

into SM states. Visible DPs are therefore defined as having a mass greater than around 1 MeV (the mass of two electrons, the lightest leptons), and invisible DPs have a mass lower than this threshold. We focus on the visible DP, since invisible DPs cannot decay into any known SM charged fermion, and would be seen in the detector as missing energy.

We looked for visible DPs between the masses of 1 MeV and 200 MeV. The limit of 200 MeV is placed because if the mass exceeds 200 MeV, the branching ratio (BR) of the DP into the electron pair is not 100%, and we would see muon-antimuon pairs in our simulated events as well [6].

4 Leptons in Large-Radius Jets

4.1 All Things (Semi-Visible) Jets

Quarks and gluons do not exist in their free form. The quantum field theory governing their interaction, QCD, does not allow any colourless state, and as a result quarks are always observed as mesons (2 quarks) or baryons (three quarks). This is called QCD confinement (Figures 4.1 and 4.2).

Figure 4.1: Illustration of what happens when two quarks are separated: they just form a new colourless quark pair [7].

Figure 4.2: The colourless pairs that are formed are either hadrons (3 quarks) or mesons (2 quarks), as illustrated above [7].

Particle detectors can only detect visible final states of produced particles, but we know that in interactions, a single quark or gluon can be produced or emitted. These single quarks and gluons form colourless particles the instant they are created. These colourless objects are

either mesons (composed of two quarks) or hadrons (composed of three quarks). This is a continuous process: as a single quark or gluon hadronises and creates mesons and hadrons, more single quarks and gluons are produced. This "shower" leads to what we call a jet, a narrow cone of mesons and hadrons, with energy deposits in the hadronic calorimeters of the detector (see Figure 4.3). The jets are created using the anti- k_T jet clustering algorithm [8], with the jet radius being a crucial parameter used to decide on the size of the jet. In this project, we set $\Delta R = 1.0$, meaning that the particles in the jet should be within a distance $\Delta R = 1.0$ from each other. In ATLAS analyses, the usual value for ΔR is 0.4, and so we call our jets large-radius jets.

Figure 4.3: Event display of 12 jets in the ATLAS detector [9].

The main principle underlying reconstruction in a detector is conservation of momentum and energy. The principle of conservation of momentum-energy dictates that the total p_T for all the particles after the collision is zero. The missing transverse momentum (MET) is then defined as the negative of the sum of the scalar p_T of all other objects in the detector. Contributions to the MET are any particle that would not be picked up by the detector.

The question is, what happens if we have any dark matter (hidden sector) particles that form part of these jets? What if parton evolution includes dark sector emissions, resulting in these DM particles being inside the jet, but not contributing to the measured energy deposits? We need some effective field theory that would describe these emissions, a way of simulating this theory, and a way of testing these predictions. Dark QCD is a young theory developed to try and explain this hidden sector [10]. Described as a "nightmare scenario" by some [11], due to the challenging testing scenarios and the vastness of possibilities, others are more optimistic. Pythia 8 [12] has a specific module for dark QCD events and allows us to simulate events in the hypothetical dark sector.

So we have the theory (dark QCD) and the way of simulating these events (Pythia HV), but we still need an experimental signature to "see" these dark sector events. If we have dark sector particles "mixed in" with the hadronic jets, we get a final state called a Semi-Visible Jet (SVJ) [13]. We introduce a parameter, R_{inv} , as the ratio between the dark sector particles and the normal SM particles produced [14].

The basic idea behind SVJs in this project, and in the context of DPs, is that unstable dark sector particles decay into stable dark sector particles (which we call dark hadrons) and DPs. So for $R_{inv} = 0.7$, we expect 70% of the unstable dark sector hadrons to decay partially

to DPs and 30% to decay to stable dark hadrons. Experimentally, we see SVJs as having a significant amount of MET aligned along one of the jets [13].

4.2 Model 1: Leptons in SVJs

Semi-visible jets (SVJs) arise in strongly-interacting dark matter scenarios. Following a recent publication on leptons in SVJs [15], we have looked at a simpler model of generating DPs in SVJs with leptons.

We generated a Z' mediator that decays to two dark quarks. Using the Hidden Valley Module of Pythia8 [12] [16], we let the two dark quarks decay to a neutral dark sector pion that decays into a strange quark and a charged dark pion. The charged dark pion decays into a stable dark hadron and a dark photon, which produces a lepton pair. This results in leptons cloaked by the SVJ.

We look at some basic kinematic variables with the ultimate goal of seeing if we can reconstruct the invariant mass of the mediator.

4.2.1 Event Generation and Model Details

The events were generated using the Hidden Valley module of Pythia8, which allows the study of visible consequences of radiation and hadronisation in a hidden sector [16].

After performing some initial feasibility studies with the Z' mass being 1 GeV, 3 GeV and 5 GeV, we decided to only use the 3 GeV mass for this project. The R_{inv} values were 0, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7 and 1.0, so that the effect of R_{inv} could clearly be seen.

4.2.2 Expected Signal Characteristics

We expect to see two large radius jets produced back-to-back, with four electrons in each jet (highlighted in blue in Figure 4.4). There should be some MET that is not from detector and reconstruction effects, due to the presence of the stable dark neutral pions (highlighted in yellow).

Due to the boost of the heavy mass Z' boson, and subsequently the boost of the light DP produced, the electron pairs from the DPs will have a small separation, quantified by ΔR . As a result, we expect to have between two and four electrons in each large-radius jet. Experimentally, the challenge is in reconstructing the electrons in the midst of hadronic activity.

Figure 4.4: Diagram

4.2.3 Results

All of the distributions plotted show the signal characteristics for the five different R_{inv} values used.

Electron Multiplicity

As explained in the model outline, we expect to see a peak value of 8 electrons in the simulation. However, when looking at the electron multiplicity plots (Figure 4.5), it is clear that this is not the case for the lower R_{inv} values. For $R_{inv} = 1$, there are no strange quarks produced alongside the charged dark pions and a dark photon is produced for every π_D^0 . In the graph we see that the peak value for $R_{inv} = 1$ is 7 electrons, which affirms this. As the R_{inv} value decreases to 0.3 inclusive, we see the peak number of electrons decrease, until it reaches a peak of 3 electrons for $R_{inv} = 0.3$. Since R_{inv} defines the ratio in which DPs are produced, it follows that for lower R_{inv} , less events containing DPs are produced. When $R_{inv} = 0$, there are no charged dark pions produced, only strange quarks, and so we do not expect to find a large electron multiplicity. This is evident from the simulated events.

Figure 4.5: Electron multiplicity

Large-Radius Jet Multiplicity

From the model description, we expected to see a peak number of two large radius jets from our set-up. In Figure 4.6, we see this is indeed the case for all 5 R_{inv} values, but we note that in the case $R_{inv} = 0$, there are fewer events with these two large-radius jets. There are events with more jets since other visible final state objects can form large-radius jets.

Figure 4.6: Large-radius jet multiplicity

Electrons in the Large-Radius Jets

The analysis is set up in a way that includes the dark photon in the large-radius jet, as shown in Figure 4.4. The expectation is to have 4 electrons in each large-radius jet. We introduce the distinction between the leading and sub-leading large-radius jets: the leading large-radius jet has the highest transverse momentum (p_T), and the sub-leading the second-highest p_T . In Figures 4.7 and 4.8, we note that for $R_{inv} = 0$, there are no dark photons produced and subsequently no electrons, and so there are no events. For $R_{inv} = 1$, the peak number of electrons in the leading large radius jets is 4, and the number of electrons decreases to 3 for

the lower R_{inv} values. For the sub-leading large-radius jet, the peak number of electrons is 3 for the range of R_{inv} . The number of electrons is lower for the sub-leading jet, because some electrons are probably outside the jet or too soft to be tagged. Note that lower R_{inv} values also have a lower amount of entries in the histogram. This once again points back to the fact that there are fewer dark photons being produced at these ratios.

Figure 4.7: Electrons in leading large-radius jet

Figure 4.8: Electrons in sub-leading large-radius jet

Angular Separation between the Large-Radius Jets

The azimuthal angle, Φ , is defined as the angle between the beam and final state object, with $\Delta\Phi$ being the difference between two Φ s. The large-radius jets are expected to be produced back-to-back in the detector, or with an angular separation $\Delta\Phi \approx \pi$. From Figure 4.9, we indeed see that for all R_{inv} values, $\Delta\Phi$ between the large-radius jets peaks at around π .

Figure 4.9: $\Delta\Phi$ between the large-radius jets

Separation between the Electrons in the Jets

The separation between the electron pairs in the large-radius jets, ΔR , is expected to be small, since the pair will be collimated. When plotting the ΔR for the electrons, which is the distance between two four-vectors, shown in Figure 4.10, we see that the pair of electrons are produced almost on top of each other, as expected.

Figure 4.10: ΔR between the two electrons in the jets

Transverse Momentum Distributions

Figures 4.11, 4.12 and 4.13 shows the p_T distributions for the electrons, the leading and sub-leading large radius jets. We see that the electron distribution is steeply falling, and that for all R_{inv} values, the electrons are produced with a low p_T . For the leading and sub-leading large-radius jets, there is a more pronounced peak than for the electrons. In the case of R_{inv} , for both plots, the distribution peaks (around 400 GeV and 300 GeV respectively) and is then steeply falling. For the other R_{inv} values, the distributions peak more to the left (at a higher p_T) and are "flatter" in shape.

Figure 4.11: Electron p_T

Figure 4.12: Leading large-radius jet p_T

Figure 4.13: Sub-leading large-radius jet p_T

Missing Transverse Momentum Distribution

The missing transverse momentum for the R_{inv} values (Figure 4.14) shows that for $R_{inv} = 0$, there is no missing energy as expected, since there are no charged dark pions produced, and as a result no stable dark pions. In the case of $R_{inv} = 1$, the distribution peaks in a similar place to the other values of R_{inv} , but the distribution is more steeply falling. R_{inv} is an interesting case: the event doesn't have enough activity, since only dark hadrons and dark photons are being produced.

Figure 4.14: Missing transverse momentum (MET)

Angular Separation between MET and the Leading Large-Radius Jet

As per the definition of semi-visible jets, we expect to see the MET aligned with one of the large-radius jets. We choose the leading instead of sub-leading large-radius jet out of convention. This is indeed the case. In Figure 4.15, we see that for all R_{inv} values (except 0), the angle between the MET and the leading large-radius jet peaks close to 0, and there is a steep drop off after 1.5 radians.

Figure 4.15: $\Delta\Phi$ between MET and the leading large-radius jet

Invariant Mass Reconstruction

Arguably the most important plot of this project, we tried to reconstruct the invariant mass of the Z' mediator using the two large-radius jets. In the Pythia code, we set the Z' mass to be 3000 GeV. This is clearly not reconstructed for any of the R_{inv} values. But this trend can be explained by understanding what happens as R_{inv} changes. For higher R_{inv} , there are more charged dark pions produced than SM quarks, which means that there are more stable dark pions that are not picked up by the detector. This leads to a higher MET value, which is not included in the invariant mass reconstruction of the large-radius jets. As seen in the distribution in Figure 4.16, the lower R_{inv} , the higher the invariant mass of the large-radius jet.

Figure 4.16: Invariant mass of the large-radius jet

5 Model 2: Mono-Lepton Jets

In our second model, we explore a novel topology where we assume that we have a long-lived dark Higgs boson and a prompt dark photon that decays into two leptons. If a particle is long-lived, it means that the particle has a "macroscopic" lifetime, and that it can travel a measurable distance through a detector before decaying. A prompt particle is one that decays immediately (promptly) after it is formed. There have been a few searches for LLPs done by ATLAS [17]. Our dark Higgs would play the part of a weakly interacting massive particle (a WIMP), and we use this long-lived dark Higgs as a source of MET that balances out the DP that decays into a lepton pair.

Experimentally, we have some difficulties in reconstructing the leptons in the detector. If a light DP is Lorentz boosted, the separation between the electrons would be too small for the detector to resolve and they would be reconstructed as a single electron. In the jet reconstruction, this would be seen as a single jet. We use the jet as a proxy for the dilepton system, and call it the lepton jet to distinguish from the usual hadronic calorimeter jets. Usual searches look at multiplicity of objects based on the signal characteristics, but here looking for two leptons (electrons) will make us miss the event.

5.1 Event Generation and Model Details

The events were showered using Pythia8, and were generated with up to two additional jets. We again make use of a hypothetical Z' mediator that decays into a heavy dark matter particle (our long-lived dark Higgs) that goes undetected, and a light dark photon that hopefully decays into two collimated leptons, forming a lepton jet. As such, we call this a mono-lepton jet search since the small angular separation of the lepton will show up as a single lepton in the detector. Mono-lepton searches are rare, but can offer significant insight in understanding how quarks interact with DM [18].

The dark Higgs was generated to have a mass of 2000 GeV, and the light DP having a mass of 200 MeV. It is not possible to reconstruct the mass of the DP at the detector level, because the detector is not sensitive enough for that low mass. The largest background for our final states is $W+$ jets, and this was generated using Pythia8 and plotted along with the signal events.

Figure 5.1: Diagram

5.2 Expected Signal Characteristics

Due to the presence of the stable dark hadron, we expect to see a reasonable amount of MET along with the two collimated leptons. The MET and the lepton jet should be on opposite sides of the detector.

5.3 Results

The signal characteristics for the signal and background samples are shown below. Note that the histograms are normalised with respect to number of events, so that the background and signal samples can be compared. In all of the distributions, we would expect the background entries to be comparable to the signal entries, but this is not the case. This is because of the cuts applied to the sample reduces the number of background events that pass all selection criteria. The cut which affects the background the most is the cut applied to the MET. We expect a large MET, since our dark Higgs is generated to have a mass of 2000 GeV, and the only part contributing to MET from the $W + \text{jets}$ sample would be neutrinos. As such most of the events generated for the background sample will not meet this criteria. That is why the background contribution in the following distributions is so low compared to the signal. This is already a promising sign that this topology is largely unexplored.

Lepton Multiplicity

In Figure 5.2, we see a peak number of two leptons in each event, as we would expect. We also see that the background events also have two leptons, but there are far fewer of them in comparison to the signal simulation.

Figure 5.2: Lepton multiplicity

Jet Multiplicity

The jet multiplicity is shown in Figure 5.3. The reason for the peak at 3 is because we generated the events with two additional jets, so that the system is boosted enough.

Figure 5.3: Jet multiplicity

Missing Transverse Momentum Distribution

The distribution of the missing transverse momentum is shown in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: MET

Separation of the Two Leading Leptons

As expected, the distance between the leptons that decayed from the DP is small, as seen in Figure 5.5. This shows that the two leptons are highly-collimated, and this implies that the detection signature would be a lepton jet. The background events that passed the selection criteria are essentially negligible.

Figure 5.5: ΔR between the two leading leptons

Angular Separation between the Two Leading Leptons

In Figure 5.6, we see that the angular separation, $\Delta\Phi$ of the two leptons is also extremely small, as we would expect from two highly-collimated leptons, again implying the lepton-jet signature. We also note that the background events are low for the criteria we imposed.

Figure 5.6: $\Delta\Phi$ between the two leading leptons

Angular Separation between the Missing Transverse Momentum and the Leading Lepton

From the distribution in Figure 5.7, it is clear that the MET and lepton jet are opposite each other, with a peak around 3.1 radians, as we would expect from the interaction.

Figure 5.7: $\Delta\Phi$ between the MET and the leading lepton

Transverse Momentum Distributions

Figures 5.8, 5.9 and 5.10 show the p_T distributions of the leading and sub-leading leptons, as well as the sum of their p_T , respectively. The p_T of the two leptons together is representative of the p_T of the DP.

Figure 5.8: p_T of the leading lepton

Figure 5.9: p_T of the sub-leading lepton

Figure 5.10: p_T of the two leading leptons

Mass Distribution of the Leading Leptons

The reconstructed invariant mass of the two leptons is the invariant mass of the DP, as reconstructed in Figure 5.11. We see that the DP has an extremely light mass, as expected. We can however not observe this in the physical experiment: the mass ranges are too low for the detector to pick up.

Figure 5.11: Mass distribution of the two leading leptons

6 Summary

Dark photons allow us to glimpse into the possibilities that dark QCD hold. With an experimentally accessible signature, it should be possible to find dark matter particles at accelerators. The two models shown in this project are examples of what a simple dark photon decaying to two leptons model can be. The analysis results are promising, showing that we can use the current simulation tools available to us (Hidden Valley in Pythia 8) to simulate these dark shower events in the first model. More work is required to fully develop these models, but these initial feasibility studies are a step in the right direction to finding the dark photon.

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